

Case Report

Tongue Tie: An Overview of Diagnosis Management & Clinical Implication

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Abstract

Tongue tie, or ankyloglossia, is a congenital condition characterized by an abnormally short, thick, or tight band of tissue (frenulum) that tethers the tongue to the floor of the mouth. This condition can significantly impact an individual's ability to move their tongue freely, leading to various functional and developmental issues, including difficulties with breastfeeding, speech articulation, and oral hygiene.

Introduction:

The tongue, a remarkably versatile muscular organ located within the oral cavity, plays a crucial role in essential functions such as speech, swallowing, and mastication. Its complex movements are a testament to the intricate interplay of muscles, nerves, and connective tissues.¹ However, for some individuals, the development of the lingual frenulum, the band of tissue beneath the tongue, may pose a limitation to the tongue's range of motion. This congenital condition, known as ankyloglossia or "tongue tie," has been a subject of interest and debate in the fields of pediatrics, dentistry, speech pathology, and lactation consulting.²

Ankyloglossia is characterized by an abnormally short, thick, or tight lingual frenulum, which restricts the tongue's ability to move freely within the oral cavity. Historically, the concept of tongue tie has been recognized for centuries. Despite this longstanding awareness, the diagnosis and management of ankyloglossia have evolved over time, with modern advances in medicine shedding new light on its clinical significance.³

In recent years, the topic of tongue tie has gained prominence as researchers and healthcare practitioners have sought to better understand its impact on various aspects of an individual's life, from infancy to adulthood. The recognition of tongue tie's potential effects on breastfeeding, speech development, dental health, and overall quality of life has led to increased interest in its assessment and management.

Case Description

A 12 year old female reported to the Department Of Pedodontics And Preventive Dentistry, Inderprastha Dental College and Hospital, Sahibabad, with a chief complain of dirty teeth and also had difficulty in tongue movement and speaking. Because of limited tongue movement, the patient complained of difficulty in maintaining oral hygiene. intraoral examination revealed short lingual frenum and restricted tongue movements.

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Class 2 Moderate=10mm Ankyloglossia (based on Kotlow's Classification)

Heart shape appearance on protrusion of the tongue

Incision being by diode Lasers.

Immediate post operative picture

Recall after 1 week

Pre- operative picture

Post- operative picture (after 1 week)

Treatment

According to the Lambert-Beer rule, the intensity of the laser and the concentration of chromophores in the tissues determine the penetration depth for an established wavelength. For the same energy given to an established surface or volume of a tissue, the type of effect on the tissue will be related above all to the time in which this energy will be administered. Long periods of application will cause photochemical effects, short

periods will mostly produce mechanical effects. The analysis of the absorption spectrum shows the penetration potential of the different wavelength. It is possible to individuate an "optical window" and so a range of wavelengths capable to go deep into. The penetration depth according to the Lambert-Beer rule, is related to the concentration of chromophores and so to the substances capable to absorb the used radiation (power density)⁴⁻⁵.

The application time does not influence the depth of penetration when there are the same tissues conditions. Another factor that can influence the penetration depth is the scattering and so the possibilities of the parts of the tissues to dissipate the radiation with or without maintaining the original energy (elastic or non-elastic scattering). A diffuse radiation (Diodes 810 nm, Nd:YAG) that has a strong absorption penetrates more deeply due to the phenomenon called “forward scattering” and can penetrate even deeper due to the types of emission and intensity used. So, in this case diodes leaser was used.

Discussion

Ankyloglossia, commonly referred to as "tongue tie," is a congenital condition characterized by an abnormally short or tight lingual frenulum, the band of tissue beneath the tongue. This condition has garnered significant attention in recent years due to its potential impact on breastfeeding, speech development, and overall oral health. In this discussion, we will delve into the clinical significance, management options, controversies, and future directions related to ankyloglossia.⁶

Most widely accepted classification Kotlow Classification

Normal, clinical acceptable range of “free tongue” >16mm	
Class I: mild ankyloglossia	12-16 mm
Class II: moderate ankyloglossia	8-11 mm
Class III: severe ankyloglossia	3-7 mm
Class IV: complete ankyloglossia	<3 mm

Classification of ankyloglossia according to KOTLOW (based on the “free tongue” length).

Management Options:⁷

Frenotomy: Frenotomy, the surgical release of the lingual frenulum, is a straightforward and minimally invasive procedure that can improve tongue mobility. It is commonly recommended for infants with breast feeding difficulties.

Physical Therapy: Physical therapy exercises to improve tongue function and mobility are sometimes used as a conservative treatment option, especially when frenotomy is not immediately necessary.

Speech Therapy: Older children and adults with ankyloglossia may benefit from speech therapy to

address articulation and speech related challenges. **Orthodontic Intervention:** In cases where ankyloglossia contributes to dental problems or malocclusion, orthodontic treatment may be necessary.

There are few Controversies: Over diagnosis and Overtreatment: There is an ongoing debate about the threshold for diagnosing and treating ankyloglossia, particularly in infants. Concerns have been raised about the potential for overdiagnosis and overtreatment, leading to unnecessary frenotomies.

Lack of Long-Term Data: There is a need for more research on the long-term outcomes and potential complications of frenotomy, especially in infants. This includes assessing speech development, dental health, and quality of life.

Inter disciplinary Approach: Collaborative decision-making involving various healthcare professionals, including paediatricians, lactation consultants, speech therapists, and oral surgeons, is essential. However, achieving consensus among these disciplines can be challenging.

Future Research Directions: Long-Term Outcomes: Further research is needed to evaluate the lasting effects of ankyloglossia treatment across the lifespan, including its impact on speech development, dental health, and overall quality of life.

Standardized Assessment Tools: Developing standardized assessment tools for diagnosing ankyloglossia can improve consistency in diagnosis and treatment recommendations.

Genetic and Environmental Factors: Investigating the genetic and environmental factors contributing to ankyloglossia can enhance our understanding of its etiology and potentially lead to preventive measures.

Clinical Significance:

Breastfeeding: Ankyloglossia can significantly affect breastfeeding. Infants with severe tongue tie may have difficulty latching onto the breast, leading to maternal pain, poor milk transfer, and potential complications. Frenotomy, a minor surgical procedure to release the frenulum, is often considered as an intervention to improve breastfeeding outcomes.

Speech Development: Ankyloglossia can persist into childhood and adulthood, potentially affecting speech development. Individuals with tongue tie may experience articulation difficulties, speech impediments, and challenges in pronouncing certain sounds. Speech therapy is a common approach to address these issues.

Dental Health: Ankyloglossia may contribute to dental problems, including a higher risk of dental caries and malocclusion (misalignment of teeth). Orthodontic evaluation and treatment may be necessary to address these concerns.⁸

Psychological and Social Implications: The psychological and social consequences of untreated ankyloglossia are not to be underestimated. Individuals may experience self-esteem issues, social difficulties, and even speech-related anxiety.

Conclusion

In conclusion, ankyloglossia is a multifaceted condition with significant clinical implications, but its diagnosis and management require careful consideration. An individualized approach is essential to avoid unnecessary interventions, particularly in infants. Future research should aim to provide a more comprehensive understanding of ankyloglossia and its optimal management strategies, considering both short-term and long-term outcomes.

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